

HomininWaterCrossingABM v1.1.0

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Model Guidance

The model is an updated version of the model introduced by Hölzchen et al. (Hölzchen et al., 2021). It simulates the crossing of a water barrier by agents representing hominins and is designed to quantitatively test the chance of agents crossing a water barrier on either an artificial or geographical map. The agents can be assigned with different modes of movement across the water ranging from undirected paddling to basic rafting. We extended the model by incorporating geographic maps, predefining behavioral scenarios and further visualizations and applied the model for conducting sets of experiments to estimate crossing success in the context of Late Pleistocene humans expanding out of Africa across sea straits (Hölzchen et al., 2022).

How it works

The model simulates the movement of agents across a landscape separated by a water barrier. Patches represent one square kilometer of real space and one tick (time-step) equals one hour of real time. The environment consists of either an artificial map or a geographic GIS reconstruction and contains resource qualities, slope and water. Furthermore, the water contains water temperature, current speed and -direction. The map is divided into a source area and a target area.

When the model is initialized, agents are randomly placed in the source area. The agents move by selecting a target patch within their radius of perception (*perception-radius*). On land, the selection of a target patch is partly determined by the distribution of resource qualities and partly random. By default, 10% of the patches within the radius of perception are randomly selected as a target. Targets may be either a land- or a water patch. As soon as the target patch is reached a new target patch is selected. A target patch may not be reached because topography does not allow it. In this case, a new target patch is selected after a time threshold has elapsed. The process is repeated until the agent dies, leaves the map or the simulation is finished. The movement speed is determined by slope, whereas the steeper the ground, the slower the agents move.

In the water, the agents move according to their behavioral scenario. Depending on their behavioral scenario, agents who cannot make it to land in time may die from dehydration, hypothermia, or exhaustion. Furthermore, agents may leave the map at the margins. By default, the population size is constant, so agents that have died or left the map are replaced by new randomly placed agents in the source area.

Successful crossings are counted as soon as there are agents in the number of a founder population (*number-founder-agents*) in the target area. The *crossing-success-rate* (CSR) results from the number of crossing attempts of potential founder populations and successful crossings. The simulation ends after 2160 ticks by default.

A detailed description of the model mechanics, factors, constants and responses can be found in the ODD+D protocol belonging to Hölzchen et al. (2022, Supplement D).

How to use it

After loading the NLOGO file into NetLogo, select a map using the *map-scenario* chooser.

Either an artificial map can be used, or a geographically explicit one based on GIS maps. The model allows to manipulate the properties of the water independently. However, if one wants to have the map data from the GIS dataset, select “from-map” for both choosers *water-temperature-scenario* and *current-scenario*. Note to set also an appropriate radius of perception (*perception-radius*) so that the agents see the opposite shore (see Hölzchen et al., 2022, Table 4).

The behavioral scenario of the agents can either be set manually using the factors listed in the interface under “Movement”, “Physiology (in the water)” and “Demographics” or one of the predefined behavioral scenarios can be selected in the chooser *movement-scenario*. If a predefined behavioral scenario is selected, the button *update-movement-scenario* must be pressed to apply the corresponding factor levels. The duration of the simulation is set by the factor *max-simulation-duration*.

After configuring the environment and agents, press the *setup* button to initialize the model and then press *go* to start the simulation run. A simulation run can be interrupted by pressing the *go* button again.

The parameter settings of the experiments described in Hölzchen et al. (2022) are provided in Supplement A (Table S6) and in the BehaviorSpace of the model (Supplement C). A detailed description of the buttons, inputs, monitors and options for visualization can be found ODD+D protocol belonging to Hölzchen et al. (2022, Supplement D).

Model Sensitivity summarized from Hölzchen et al. (2021)

The sensitivity analyses of the base model describe the general behavior of the model with respect to crossing success when factors are varied in a generalized spatial environment.

Both environmental and agent behavioral factors affect the *crossing-success-rate*, albeit to varying degrees. The results serve as a basis for the targeted design of simulation experiments with this model. The results of this analysis serve as a basis for the targeted design of simulation experiments using this model, as well as for predicting the effects of changes in environmental and behavioral factors on crossing success. Below we have summarized the main results to give an overview of the model behavior. A detailed description of the base model behavior can be found in Hölzchen et al. (2021).

Sensitivity of Environmental Factors

While crossing success is also dependent on agent configuration and behavioral scenario, general effects were found to occur in all behavioral scenarios tested due to the respective environmental configuration, though to varying degrees. Both the width of the sea strait and the speed of the current determine the distance needed to be traversed for crossing. An increase of the width of the water barrier leads to a linear decrease of crossing success up to a width where no crossing is possible. Accordingly, increasing the current speed leads to a linear decrease in crossing success. In the submerged scenarios, such as random paddling or swimming, a decrease in water temperature results in a decrease in crossing success. The sensitivity of the environmental factors of width of the sea strait, current speed, and water temperature showed that environmental effects realistically affect the crossing success of the agents, confirming their suitability as relevant environmental factors for simulating sea crossings.

Sensitivity of Agent Configuration and Behavioral Scenarios

The properties of the agents as well as their behavior determines how much the environmental factors prevent them from crossing. The sensitivity studies showed that the most crucial factor for crossing success is the directionality of the movement, as in the behavioral scenarios with directed movement the agents achieved several times higher crossing successes than in undirected scenarios. A prerequisite for directed movement is the perception of the opposite shore. When applying the model in a geographically explicit context, it is therefore necessary to first determine whether the opposite shore can be perceived in order to apply directed behavioral scenarios, such as directed swimming or rafting. The sensitivity studies showed also that random crossings were possible, however, considerably lower crossing success rates of less than 50% compared to the directed crossings were recorded. It was also shown that a randomness of decision of 10% was sufficient to simulate such accidental crossings and an increase in this factor did not considerably affect the success of crossings.

In addition to the directionality of movement, agent behavior is determined by factors of movement, physiology and demography. In the submerged scenarios, hypothermia was the main limiting physiological factor, whereas in rafting, dying of dehydration was the most common cause of death. Exhaustion due to muscle activity and thermoregulation played a minor role and only happened when hypothermia or dehydration could be avoided.

The sensitivity studies have shown that the evaluation of chances for crossing a sea strait not only depends on a single factor, such as the distance from coast to coast or whether hominins used watercraft. Instead, several environmental and behavioral factors need to be considered in order to assess the success of the crossing in a differentiated manner. The

generalized test environment that the model offers showed plausible effects on crossing success in the tested environmental and behavioral configurations allowing for a gradual distinction of crossing success. Therefore, the model can be used for geographically explicit contexts to test hypotheses of the skills of hominins to cross sea straits.

References

- Hölzchen, E., Hertler, C., Mateos, A., Rodríguez, J., Berndt, J.O., Timm, I.J., 2021. Discovering the opposite shore: How did hominins cross sea straits? *PloS one* 16 (6), e0252885.
- Hölzchen, E., Hertler, C., Willmes, C., Anwar, I.P., Mateos, A., Rodríguez, J., Berndt, J.O., Timm, I.J., 2022. Estimating crossing success of human agents across sea straits out of Africa in the Late Pleistocene. *Palaeogeography, Palaeoclimatology, Palaeoecology*.